

Satyam and Kishori, two high-yielding varieties developed for the rainfed lowlands of Bihar, India

R. Thakur, A.K. Singh, R.S. Singh, S.B. Mishra, N.K. Singh, and J.N. Rai, Rice Research Unit, Rajendra Agricultural University (RAU), Bihar, Pusa (Samastipur) 848125, India

Rainfed lowlands constitute nearly half of the total rice area in Bihar (2.7 million ha). The rice crop depends on the monsoon. When the monsoon is delayed, rice planting is also delayed. No high-yielding varieties (HYVs) are suitable for delayed conditions mainly because they flower at the end of October when low temperature sets in, causing nonuniform flowering and poor seed setting. Farmers therefore rely on traditional photoperiod-sensitive, tall cultivars that are tolerant of cold at flowering. HYVs are consequently grown under favorable conditions only.

To develop HYVs adapted to delayed monsoon conditions, crosses involving traditional cultivars (as one of the parents) were made in the early 1980s. Several cultures derived from IR8/Barogar and RD19/Desaria were tested under both normal and delayed monsoon conditions against standard

checks in a regional trial. Based on average performance, many cultures were promoted to state multilocal variety trials with three replications in 1993. From 1993 to 1996, RAU1119-13-3-1 (Kishori) derived from IR8/Barogar and RAU3025-2-1B-2-1 (Satyam) derived from RD19/Desaria were superior to Radha and Pankaj (Table 1), the standard checks recommended earlier for normal planting conditions. Satyam had a 10.8% and 13.8% yield

advantage over Radha and Pankaj, respectively, whereas Kishori yielded 13.5% and 16.6% more than the checks. These varieties were also tested in the multilocal Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR)-IRRI collaborative shuttle breeding trial in eastern India, under both normal (30-d-old seedlings) and delayed planting (60-d-old seedlings) against checks adapted to rainfed lowland conditions, including Sabita, a photoperiod-

Table 1. Performance of Satyam and Kishori in state multilocal varietal trials conducted under normal planting conditions, 1993-96.

Year	Site	Yield (t ha ⁻¹) ^a				LSD (at 5%)	CV (%)
		Satyam	Kishori	Radha	Pankaj		
1993	Patna	3.3	3.5	3.6	2.8	1.3	16.60
	Pusa	5.6	3.8	4.6	3.6	0.6	07.30
	Sabour	4.9	4.5	5.2	5.4	0.5	06.58
	Bikramganj	6.0	2.7	6.1	5.3	0.9	08.34
1994	Patna	5.6	4.8	3.7	3.5	0.3	05.48
	Sabour	3.4	3.8	2.3	2.8	0.7	13.29
	Bikramganj	4.3	4.6	2.7	4.5	1.1	19.40
1995	Patna	2.0	3.9	2.0	1.8	0.6	20.00
	Jhanjharpur	3.7	4.6	2.9	3.0	0.4	14.30
	Pusa	3.1	4.1	1.6	-	0.1	13.09
	Sabour	3.9	-	4.0	3.3	0.4	18.00
1996	Bikramganj	3.6	-	4.8	3.1	0.2	04.34
	Pusa	4.3	4.3	4.1	4.1	0.3	16.87
	Patna	3.4	4.0	3.0	3.7	0.2	17.64
	Dhangain	5.5	5.7	5.8	5.3	0.3	12.83
	Jhanjharpur	4.6	4.5	3.6	3.8	0.2	11.94
	Pooled mean	4.1	4.2	3.7	3.6	-	-
	Pooled LSD (5%)	1.3	1.1	1.5	1.6	-	-

^aMean of three replicates.

Table 2. Yield performance (t ha⁻¹) of Kishori and Satyam in ICAR-IRRI collaborative shuttle breeding trial in eastern India, 1994-96.

Year	Site	Kishori		Satyam		Rajshree		Mahsuri		Sabita		LSD (at 5%)		CV (%)	
		I ^a	II ^b	I	II	I	II	I	II	I	II	I	II	I	II
1994	Masodha	-	5.6	7.0	4.1	5.3	4.4	5.0	3.2	4.4	4.2	0.8	0.5	09.0	09.3
	Patna	5.9	2.1	4.3	4.0	3.9	3.3	6.6	2.0	5.8	0.9	1.5	0.9	17.4	27.5
	Pusa	4.5	3.8	6.1	4.3	4.3	3.1	3.0	2.2	2.7	2.8	0.4	0.3	06.9	06.4
	Titabar	5.1	4.4	4.3	3.7	4.4	3.5	3.4	3.4	-	-	0.8	0.6	13.5	13.0
1995 ^c	Patna	2.8	5.8	1.7	5.1	1.9	3.8	2.2	4.7	3.0	1.5	0.3	1.5	0.3	0.6
	Pusa	6.3	3.2	5.6	2.3	3.9	2.6	3.4	1.9	1.4	1.8	0.1	0.2	16.6	07.4
	Raipur	2.1	1.9	2.3	2.3	3.0	1.9	2.6	1.9	3.0	2.2	0.9	0.9	09.7	07.9
1996	Patna	5.3	2.3	5.1	2.4	3.8	1.8	4.1	2.4	4.1	2.4	0.3	0.6	14.5	09.5
	Pusa	4.2	3.1	4.4	2.9	4.1	2.9	3.4	1.8	3.5	3.1	0.2	0.3	06.6	11.7
	Masodha	6.2	3.8	5.3	3.5	3.5	1.4	3.0	3.4	4.3	3.4	0.3	0.3	08.2	21.5
	Titabar	5.3	3.1	4.9	2.8	3.8	2.5	3.8	2.5	3.0	2.5	0.5	0.4	10.2	10.6
	Pooled mean	5.0	3.6	4.6	3.4	3.8	2.8	3.7	2.8	35.2	24.8	-	-	-	-
	Pooled LSD (5%)	1.5	1.3	1.8	1.1	0.9	1.2	1.7	1.2	1.3	1.6	-	-	-	-

^aTransplanted at 30 d after sowing. ^bTransplanted at 60 d after sowing. ^cDirect seeding vs transplanting.

sensitive variety. They outyielded checks under normal and delayed planting conditions (Table 2). Because of their superior performance in numerous on-farm trials, Satyam and Kishori were released for general

cultivation in rainfed lowlands for normal and delayed monsoon conditions.

Both have intermediate heights (120-125 cm), compact erect habit, and 145-

150-d maturity. Satyam has long fine grains and Kishori has long bold grains. They are resistant to bacterial blight and tolerant of brown spot and Zn and Fe deficiencies. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement — upland

On-farm characterization of upland rice varieties in north Thailand

K. Van Keer, Laboratory for Soil Fertility and Soil Biology, KU Leuven tout court, 3001 Leuven, Belgium; G. Trebuil and B. Courtois, IRRI, seconded from CIRAD-CA; C. Vejpas, IRRI

An on-farm diagnostic survey on the extent and causes of variability of upland rice yields was carried out during 1993-96 in Mae Haeng, Chiang Mai Province, in upper northern Thailand (600-700 masl).

Farmers' varieties were characterized from physiological, agronomic, and genetic points of view. Data were obtained over four successive wet seasons from a total of 423 small squares (1 m²) from 63 farmers' fields representing an extensive range of upland rice-cropping conditions under a predominant swidden cultivation system. Plots were monitored every 2 wk to quantify key physiological and agronomic parameters needed to understand yield buildup patterns of various types of cultivars. Isozyme analysis was carried out to assess the genetic variability of farmers' upland rice varieties.

All upland rice cultivars were found to belong to group 6 (tropical japonicas) of Glaszmann's classification. Heterogeneity was sometimes detected between samples of the same variety coming from different farms. The rare allele 3 at locus *Amp-1* typical of varieties from the Himalayan foothills was observed in some cultivars. Only two late-maturing varieties were found to be glutinous, a type of rice used to

prepare rice cakes during traditional festivals.

Two main types of cultivars, early (95-115 d) and late maturing (138-177 d), were distinguished and played different roles on the farms. Late-maturing varieties clearly constituted the most important type in terms of production volume, whereas early

maturing varieties were planted to improve food security before the main harvesting period. Early and late cultivars were found to be weakly and strongly photoperiod-sensitive, respectively. When expressed in degree days, crop duration cycle was evenly split between the vegetative and reproductive phases for early cultivars

Table 1. Physiological and genetic characteristics of local upland rice varieties in Mae Haeng Village, Chiang Mai Province, Thailand, 1993-96.

Variety	Importance	Varietal group ^a	Photoperiodism	Grain type	DD to PI ^b	DD to harvest
<i>Early maturing types</i>						
Chaloina	Rare	Tropical japonica	Weakly sensitive	Nonglutinous	650	1340
Kochokai	Rare				800	1400
Chaloloe	Dominant				670	1350
Kochole	Rare				590	1270
<i>Late maturing types</i>						
Chaae	Rare	Tropical japonica	Strongly sensitive	Nonglutinous	1060	1900
Chanoko	Common			Glutinous	1060	1910
Chafuma	Common			Nonglutinous	1000	1860
Chazu	Rare			Nonglutinous	1230	2120
Komu	Rare			Nonglutinous	1150	1960
Chanona	Rare			Glutinous	860	1790

^aBased on isozyme analysis. ^bDD = degree-days (13 °C threshold temperature), PI = panicle initiation.

Table 2. Agronomic characteristics of Chaloina and Chaae grown in Mae Haeng Village, Chiang Mai Province, Thailand, 1993-96.

Variety	Chaloina	Chaae
Duration	Early	Late
Observations (no.)	75	234
Maximum grain yield (g m ² at 0% H ₂ O)	308	438
Maximum 100-grain weight (g at 0% H ₂ O)	23.2	25.0
Threshold value ^a for filled spikelets m ⁻² (no.)	13,300	17,500
Maximum value for filled spikelets m ⁻² (no.)	16,200	20,600
Maximum grain filling (%)	81	98
Threshold value for spikelets m ⁻² (no.)	20,100	21,500
Maximum value for spikelets m ⁻² (no.)	22,000	26,700
Maximum value for spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	144	183
Threshold value for panicles m ⁻² (no.)	155	146
Maximum value for panicles m ⁻² (no.)	228	237
Maximum value for panicles plant ⁻¹ (no.)	2.8	3.6
Threshold value for plants m ⁻² (no.)	81	66

^aThreshold value = value required to achieve the maximum for a particular yield component.